

A Development of a Weight-Balancing Control System Based On Android Operating System

Authors : Rattanathip Rattanachai, Piyachai Petchyen, Kunyanuth Kularbphettong

Abstract : This paper describes the development of a Weight- Balancing Control System based on the Android Operating System and it provides recommendations on ways of balancing of user's weight based on daily metabolism process and need so that user can make informed decisions on his or her weight controls. The system also depicts more information on nutrition details. Furthermore, it was designed to suggest to users what kinds of foods they should eat and how to exercise in the right ways. We describe the design methods and functional components of this prototype. To evaluate the system performance, questionnaires for system usability and Black Box Testing were used to measure expert and user satisfaction. The results were satisfactory as followed: Means for experts and users were 3.94 and 4.07 respectively.

Keywords : weight-balancing control, Android operating system, daily metabolism, black box testing

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